

Supplementary Fig 1

Figure S1. Proliferation and maturation features of fresh-isolated and *in vitro* cortical astrocytes.

Related to Figure 1. (A-C) Characterization of FACS-sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes. (A) Relative expression levels of the key proliferation gene Ki67 in FACS-sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes. Bars show the mean of the Ki67 mRNA levels of FACS sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes at P3, P14, P20 and P50 relative to GAPDH values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the three replicates at each time point. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ ($n=6-9$ mice each group; one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's post-hoc correction). (B) Relative expression levels of the key astrocytic genes (GLT1, Cx43, Cx30, Kir4.1) in FACS-sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes. Bars show the mean of the mRNA levels of FACS sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes at P14 and P50 relative to P14 values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the three replicates at each time point. ** $p < 0.01$ ($n=3-6$ mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test).

(C) Representative RT-PCR analysis and quantification of the relative expression of the markers for astrocytes (GFAP, ALDH1L1, GLAST), oligodendrocytes (MOG) and neurons (Syt1, Calb1) in FACS-sorted ECFP-positive astrocytes in comparison with β -actin. Bars indicate that markers for oligodendrocytes and neurons are at background levels in FACS-sorted ECFP astrocytes (sorting to yield >99% pure positive cells). (D-K) Characterization of primary cortical astrocytes. (D and E) Relative expression levels of the key metabolic genes in mitochondrial biogenesis and oxidative phosphorylation. Bars show the mean of the mRNA levels of primary cortical cultured astrocytes at DIV2, DIV5-10 and DIV>20 relative to DIV2 values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the three replicates at each time point. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ (n=3 biologically independent samples; one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's post-hoc correction). (F) Indices of mitochondrial respiratory function calculated from OCR profile of primary cultured astrocytes measured at DIV5-10 and DIV>20. Bars indicate that basal respiration and maximal respiration are higher in DIV5-10 astrocytes when compared with the DIV>20 astrocytes. Each group is shown as pmol/min OCR. Error bars represent \pm SEM of the 3 replicates at each time point. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (G) Indices of glycolytic pathway activation calculated from primary cultured astrocytes ECAR performed at DIV5-10 and DIV>20. Bars indicate that basal ECAR is higher in DIV>20 when compared with DIV5-10 astrocytes. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3 replicates at each time point. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (H) ATP content calculated in primary cortical astrocytes at DIV>20 with respect to DIV5-10. Bars indicate that ATP is higher in DIV5-10 when compared with the DIV>20 astrocytes. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the 3 replicates at each time point. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (I) Lactate content in primary cortical astrocytes at DIV>20 with respect to DIV5-10. Bars indicate that lactate is higher in DIV>20 when compared with the DIV5-10 astrocytes. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the 3 replicates at each time point. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (J) (Left) Relative expression levels of the key proliferation gene Ki67 in primary cortical astrocytes. Bars show the mean of the Ki67 mRNA levels in astrocytes at DIV5-10, >DIV20

relative to H3 values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the three replicates at each time point. *** $p < 0.001$ ($n = 3$ biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t -test). (Right) Relative expression levels of the proliferating gene TOP2A in primary cortical astrocytes. Bars show the mean of TOP2A mRNA levels in astrocytes at DIV5-10 and DIV>20 relative to DIV5-10. Error bars represent means \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$ ($n = 3$ biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t -test). (K) Relative expression levels of the key astrocytic genes (GLT1, Cx43, Cx30, Kir4.1) in primary cortical astrocytes. Bars show the mean of the mRNA levels in astrocytes at DIV5-10 and DIV>20 relative to DIV5-10 values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the three replicates at each time point. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ ($n = 3$ biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t -test).

Supplementary Fig 2

Figure S2. Mitochondria in developing astrocyte versus mature astrocytes. Related to Figure 2.

(A) Confocal images show co-localisation of S100 β (a marker of astrocytes) with electroporated astrocytes containing the mito-YFP. Histogram show the co-localisation of 100% between Mito-YFP and S100 β . n= 2 mice, Scale bar: 100 μm and 20 μm (high magnification). (B) Maximal projections of confocal images showing mitochondrial morphology in L5 cortical astrocytes on P10 as visualised by means of the *in utero* electroporation of a genetically encoded mitochondrial matrix-targeted YFP and mTAGBFP2 cytoplasmic filler. Scale bar: 10 μm . Bottom: rendering of a reconstructed astrocyte and mitochondrial network. Right: rendering of the reconstructed mitochondrial network. Pseudocolour-coded representation of volume/sphericity. The fragmented mitochondria with a spherical or short round structure and a volume of 0.3-3 μm^3 are coloured red, and those with a similar shape but a volume of 4-13 μm^3 are coloured orange/yellow. Mitochondria with a short and filamentous shape and a volume of 14-80 μm^3 are coloured yellow/green; those with filamentous shape and a volume of 81-340 μm^3 are coloured light blue; and those with a long, filamentous and interconnected shape and a volume of >340 μm^3 are coloured blue/purple. Scale bar: 10 μm (C) Rendering of the two reconstructed astrocytes and mitochondrial network shown in Figure 2A at P17 and P50. Astrocytes were electroporated with mt-YFP (cyan) and mTAGBFP2 cytoplasmic filler (grey). D) High magnification of the red boxed region labelled in Figure S1C. Note that mitochondria in P50 astrocytes occupy less cytosolic volume with respect to developing astrocytes at P17.

Supplementary Fig. 3

Figure S3. PGC-1α controls mitochondrial genes, OCR, ECAR and lactate in developing astrocytes.

Related to figure 3. (A and B) Confocal images showing TAM-induced recombination in the prefrontal cortex (PFC) of aPGC1αKO-tdTomato mice at P40. (A) tdTomato fluorescence (magenta) is confined to glutamine synthase (GS)-positive astrocytes (green) in the PFC. Scale bar: 100 μm. (B) tdTomato fluorescence (magenta) is not detectable in NeuN-positive cells (neurons; green). Scale bar: 100 μm. (C) Bars indicate the efficacy of TAM-induced recombination in L1, L2/3 and L5 cortical astrocytes as evaluated on the basis of the expression of tdTomato in GS-positive astrocytes. Error bars represent mean values ± SEM. (D) Relative expression levels of PGC-1α. Bars indicate mean mRNA levels in P40 PFC tissues prepared from control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1αKO-tdTomato mice in relation to those in hGFAP-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent mean values ± SEM. **p<0.01 (n=5 mice; unpaired Student's t-test). (E and F) Confocal images represent TAM-induced recombination in cortical primary astrocytes derived from aPGC1αKO-tdTomato mice. Images show cultured astrocytes containing tdTomato recombined cells (magenta) stained with DAPI (blue), GFAP (green). Bars show the efficacy

of TAM-induced recombination in cultured astrocytes (54%) as evaluated by the expression of tdTomato in GFAP-positive cells. Scale bar: 50 μ m. (G) Relative expression levels of the key metabolic genes of oxidative phosphorylation. Bars show mRNA levels quantified in hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato primary cultured astrocytes. Error bars represent means \pm SEM **p<0.01; ***p<0.001 (n=4-6 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (H) Relative expression levels of the key metabolic genes in oxidative phosphorylation. Bars show mRNA levels quantified in the aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato primary cultured astrocytes with or without LentiPGC1 α infection. Error bars represent means \pm SEM. *p<0.05, ***p<0.001 (n=3 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (I) Indices of mitochondrial respiratory function calculated from the OCR profile of hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato astrocytes measured on DIV10. Bars indicate basal and maximal respiration; the error bars represent the mean values \pm SEM of three replicates at each time point. **p <0.01 (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (J) ATP content in hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato astrocytes measured at DIV10. Error bars represent the mean values \pm SEM of three replicates at each time point. ***p<0.001 (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test).

Supplementary Fig. 4

Figure S4. Selective and inducible deletion of PGC1 α in astrocytes do not modify cortical thickness but increase proliferation of developing astrocytes and of NG2 cells. Related to Figure 4.

(A) Schematic diagram of the generation of aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato and control hGFAP-tdTomato mice. We generated inducible knock-out mice in which astrocyte PGC-1 α was specifically deleted in a temporally controlled manner. Mice harbouring a tamoxifen(TAM)-inducible CreERT2 recombinase transgene driven by the human astrocytic glial fibrillary acidic protein (hGFAP) promoter [39] were

crossbred with mice containing cre excisable loxP sequences in the endogenous stop codon of tdTomato mice. The resulting hGFAPCre^{ERT2}tdTomatolox/+ mice were cross-bred with PGC1 α -R26tdTomatolox/+ mice, and their progeny were hGFAPCre^{ERT2}tdTomatoPGC1 α ^{lox/lox} mice and PGC1 α -R26tdTomatolox/lox mice. The hGFAPCre^{ERT2}tdTomatoPGC1 α ^{lox/lox} treated with TAM generated the aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Control mice have been generated by crossbreeding hGFAPCre^{ERT2} with tdTomatolox/lox mice and by treating the resulting hGFAPCre^{ERT2}tdTomato^{lox/lox} with TAM. (B) Confocal images showing tdTomato expressing astrocytes (grey), the immunostaining of L5 marker CTIP2 (green) and DAPI (blue) in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (C) Quantification of layer L1, L2,3 and L5 thickness in control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM (n=4-5 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (D) Quantification of survival of tdTomato expressing astrocytes in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Bars indicate the total % of tdTomato positive astrocytes stained with Caspase3. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brains slices in each mouse (n=4 mice each group, unpaired Student's t-test). (E) Quantification of proliferation of non recombined astrocytes (GS-positive⁺ and tdTomato-negative⁻) in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Bars indicate the % of tdTomato-negative and GS-positive astrocytes stained with BrdU in L1, L2/3 and L5 of PFC. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brains slices in each mouse. *p<0.05, ***p<0.001 (n=4 mice each group, unpaired Student's t-test). (F-I) Confocal images showing tdTomato expressing astrocytes (green) and the immunostaining of NG2 cells (red) in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (J) Quantification of NG2 cells in L1, L2,3 and L5 of control hGFAP-tdTomato or aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM *p<0.05 (n=3 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (K) Confocal sections show immunostaining for GS (red), DAPI (blue) and BrdU (green) and in L5 of the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice on P40. Scale bar: 50 μ m. (L) Bars indicate the % of BrdU⁺/GS⁺ cells in L1, L2/3 and L5 of the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α cKO-tdTomato mice on P14. Error bars represent the mean values \pm SEM of 3-4 brain slices

from each mouse (n=3 mice) **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 (n=3 mice each group, unpaired Student's t-test).

M) Confocal sections show immunostaining for NG2 (red), DAPI (blue) and BrdU (green) and in L5 of the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1αcKO-tdTomato mice on P40. Scale bar: 50 μm. N) Bars indicate the % of BrdU⁺/NG2⁺ cells in L1, L2/3 and L5 of the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1αcKO-tdTomato mice on P14. Error bars represent the mean values ± SEM of 3-4 brain slices from each mouse **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 (n=2 mice each group, unpaired Student's t-test).

Supplementary Fig 5

Figure S5. mGluR5 signalling modulates PGC-1 α levels, regulates mitochondrial OxPhos and ATP production and controls astrocyte morphogenesis. Related to Figure 5.

(A) Simplified scheme of mGluR5 induced activation of PGC-1 α through mTOR pathway. Diagram shows the contribution of mGluR5 signalling in the activation of PGC-1 α . (B and C) Representative western blots analysis and relative protein quantifications of hGFAP-tdTomato or mGluR5cKO-tdTomato cultured astrocytes, in presence or in absence of DHPG (50 μ M, 15 min) treatment, preceded by a pre-incubation with selective inhibitors for mGluR5 (mPEP, 10 μ M, 30 min), Ca²⁺ (BAPTA-AM, Ca²⁺ chelator, 50 μ M, 30 min), CamKII (KN93, 10 μ M, 30 min) or mTOR (Rapamycin, 100nM, 30 min). Protein expression was normalized to β -tubulin and plotted as relative change of expression levels relative to control (no treatment). Phosphoprotein levels were normalized against total protein levels. Error bars represent means \pm SEM. * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, *** p <0.001 (n =3-5 samples; one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's post-hoc correction). DHPG: (RS)-3,5-Dihydroxyphenylglycine; mPEP: 2-Methyl-6-(phenylethynyl)pyridine; BAPTA-AM: 1,2-bis(o-aminophenoxy)ethane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid; KN93: N-[2-[[[3-(4-Chlorophenyl)-2-propenyl]methylamino]methyl]phenyl]-N-(2-hydroxyethyl)-4-methoxybenzenesulphonamide. (D) Cartoon illustrating the production of primary cultured astrocytes from hGFAPCre^{ERT2}R26-tdTomato^{loxp/loxp} and hGFAPCre^{ERT2}mGluR5^{loxp/loxp} hGFAPCre^{ERT2}R26-

tdTomato^{loxp/loxp} mice treated with TAM referred respectively to hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato. (E and F) Relative expression levels of *mGluR5* mRNA and the key metabolic genes in mitochondrial biogenesis. Bars show the mean of the mRNA levels of primary cortical cultured astrocytes of control hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato primary cultured cells relative to control values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ (n=4 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (G) Relative expression levels of *mGluR5* and *PGC-1 α* in FACS sorted tdTomato positive astrocytes from control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice relative to control values. Error bars represent means \pm SEM. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=6 mice each group, unpaired Student's t-test). (H) Rendering of a reconstructed astrocyte and mitochondrial networks of amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice on P50. Scale bar 10 μ m. (I) Indices of mitochondrial respiratory function calculated from control hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato primary cultured astrocytes OCR profile measured at DIV10. Bars indicate the basal and maximal respiration; error bars represent means \pm SEM of the 3 replicates at each time point (n=6 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test).-(J) Indices of glycolytic pathway activation calculated from control hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato primary cultured astrocytes ECAR profile measured at DIV10. Bars indicate the basal ECAR; error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3 replicates at each time point. * $p < 0.05$ (n=5 biologically independent samples; unpaired Student's t-test). (K) ATP content hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato astrocytes measured at DIV10. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of the 3 replicates at each time point. (n=5 biologically independent samples). (L) Quantification of proliferation of tdTomato expressing astrocytes in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Bars indicate the % of tdTomato- positive astrocytes stained with BrdU in cortical L1, L2,3 and L5. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$ (n=4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (M) Quantification of proliferation of GS expressing astrocytes in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Bars indicate the % of GS- positive astrocytes stained with BrdU in cortical L1, L2,3 and L5. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$ (n=4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (N)

Quantification of proliferation of NG2 expressing cells in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Bars indicate the % of NG2- positive and tdTomato-negative cells stained with BrdU in cortical L1, L2,3 and L5. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$ (n=4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (O) Quantification of tdTomato-positive astrocytes in L1, L2,3 and L5 of PFC sections of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=6 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (P) Quantification of GS- positive astrocytes in L1, L2,3 and L5 of PFC sections of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. ** $p < 0.01$ (n=6 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (Q) Quantification of NG2- positive cells in L1, L2,3 and L5 of PFC sections of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 3-5 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$ (n=6 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (R) Representative confocal images showing territory coverage by astrocytes in L5 in the PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice at P40. Scale bar: 50 μ m. (S) Representative 3D surface rendering showing volume reconstruction of L5 cortical astrocytes from hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Scale bar: 10 μ m. (T) Distance between cell bodies of tdTomato astrocytes in control hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 4 brain slices in each mouse. *** $p < 0.001$ (n=4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test) (U) (Top) High magnification of single astrocytes. Scale bar: 20 μ m. (Down) Sholl analysis tracing with digitally applied centering rings spaced 10 μ m apart, centered on the soma of single tdTomato astrocytes. Scale bar 10 μ m. (V) Sholl analysis reveals decreased astrocytes complexity of amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice in respect of control hGFAP-tdTomato. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 4 brain slices in each mouse ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (n=4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (W) Confocal images showing TAM-induced td-Tomato recombination (grey) and DAPI staining (blue) in hGFAP-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato PFC at P40. Scale bar: 100 μ m. (X) Confocal images showing tdTomato expressing astrocytes (grey), the immunostaining of L5 marker C1P2 (green) and DAPI (blue) in the

PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice (n=3 mice each group). Scale bar: 100 μ m. (Y) Quantification of layer L1, L2/3 and L5 thickness in control hGFAP-tdTomato or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM (n=4-5 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test).

Supplementary Fig 6

Figure S6. Astrocytic PGC-1 α controls excitatory synapse numbers. Related to Figure 6.

(A-D) Decreased number of excitatory synapses in the tdTomato astrocyte territories of aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato mice with respect to control hGFAP-tdTomato mice. (A and C) Confocal images show intracortical excitatory synapses (VGLUT1, green and PSD95, red) and thalamocortical excitatory synapses (VGLUT2, green and PSD95, red) inside tdTomato astrocyte territories of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato mice. Scale bar: 2 μ m. Dotted lines show astrocyte territory boundaries and arrows mark co-localized synaptic puncta. (B and D) Quantification of intracortical (B) and thalamocortical (D) synaptic co-localized puncta within tdTomato astrocyte territories in the L5 of PFC of control hGFAP-tdTomato and aPGC1 α KO-tdTomato mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 4 brain slices in each mouse *p<0.05, **p<0.01 (n=3-4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test).

(E) Cumulative frequency plot of mEPSCs rise time from the traces Figure 6F and comparison of average mEPSCs rise time in control (2.1 \pm 0.1 ms) and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato mice (2.4 \pm 0.1 ms). (F) Cumulative

frequency plots of decay times from the traces in Figure 6F and comparison of average mEPSCs decay time in control (4.9 ± 0.3 ms, $n=8$) and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato (6.2 ± 0.3 ms, $n=13$). Data points represent individual cells. Error bars represent mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$ (unpaired Student's t-test).

Supplementary Fig 7

Figure S7. Re-expression of PGC-1α in astrocytes restores astrocyte proliferation and synaptogenesis. Related to Figure 7.

(A-B) Images showing the local expression of astrocyte-specific lentivirus (LentiGFP, green and LentiDsRed, red) in mPFC on P40. Scale bars: 500 μ m. LentiGFP is expressed in the cytosol while LentiDsRed is expressed in the nucleus. Lenti DsRed co-localizes with GS immunostaining. (C) Relative mRNA expression of PGC-1α in the PFC tissue obtained from control hGFAP-tdTomato+LentiGFP, amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiGFP and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiPGC1α. Error bars represent mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$ ($n=2-3$ mice each group, one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's post-hoc correction). (D-E) Quantification of proliferation of tdTomato-positive astrocytes (D) and tdTomato-

negative and GS-positive astrocytes (E) in hGFAP-tdTomato+LentiGFP amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiGFP or amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiPGC1 α mice. Bars indicate the % of tdTomato- and GS-positive astrocytes stained with BrdU in L2,3 and L5 of the PFC. Error bars represent mean \pm SEM of 3-4 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (n=3 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (F-G) Quantification of tdTomato-positive (F) and tdTomato-negative and GS-positive astrocytes (G) in L2,3 and L5 of PFC sections of hGFAP-tdTomato+LentiGFP, amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiGFP and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiPGC1 α mice. Error bars represent mean \pm SEM of 4 brain slices in each mouse. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ (n=3 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test). (H) Confocal images show thalamocortical excitatory synapses (VGLUT2, green and PSD95, red) inside tdTomato astrocyte territory of amGluR5cKO-tdTomato and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiPGC1 α mice. Scale bar: 2 μ m. Dotted lines show astrocyte territory boundaries and arrows mark co-localized synaptic puncta. (I) Quantification thalamocortical synaptic co-localized puncta within tdTomato astrocyte territories in the L5 of PFC of hGFAP-tdTomato+LentiGFP, amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiGFP and amGluR5cKO-tdTomato+LentiPGC1 α mice mice. Error bars represent means \pm SEM of 4 brain slices in each mouse * $p < 0.05$ (n=3-4 mice each group; unpaired Student's t-test).